

PRONUNCIATION ERRORS AND PHONETIC INSTRUCTIONS IN RUSSIAN CLASSROOMS

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The relevance of this study is connected with the growing importance of the English language as an international language and the increasing need for clear and intelligible speech among Russian-speaking learners. Although modern language teaching focuses on communication, pronunciation is often not taught systematically in Russian classrooms. Many students keep making fossilized phonetic errors, which are mainly caused by several factors, such as the influence of their native language, a teacher's complicated instructions (or the absence), and the teaching material – the very material that facilitates the learners think in English but talk appropriately. In addition, there is a gap between theoretical knowledge of phonetics and its application in the classroom. For these reasons, it is important to investigate common pronunciation errors and analyse how phonetic instruction is organized in Russian educational settings.

The problem of the study is the gap between the theoretical training that ESL teachers receive in university disciplines such as "Contrastive typology of languages" and "Methodology of teaching foreign languages", and the way this knowledge is used in pronunciation teaching. These subjects are supposed to help teachers predict difficulties caused by the learners' native language (or the areas of the L2 that need special attention and preparation) and explain those difficulties in a more efficiently. However, it is not clear whether this knowledge is consciously applied in real classroom practice. Pronunciation errors are usually viewed only as learner-centred/-related problems, while the role of teaching methods and instructional decisions is often not taken into account. That's why, it is necessary to examine pronunciation errors not only as individual learner difficulties but also as possible results of classroom instruction.

Based on the ideas of teaching ESL [5; 6], teaching phonetics [4;15], phonological disorders from neurolinguistic point of view [1; 56], material design [3; 99], and error analysis [2;163] the study formulates the model of "The Triangle of reasons of pronunciation error production in foreign language teaching: learner, instruction/instructor, and teaching material".

The recommendations of the study are:

- to analyse and categorise common pronunciation errors made by Russian-speaking learners of English;
- to investigate the sources of the pronunciation errors;
- to determine whether practicing ESL teachers apply knowledge from "Contrastive typology of languages" and "Methodology of teaching foreign languages" in their classes and pronunciation instructions;

- to determine whether upcoming teachers understand the practical purpose of the mentioned earlier disciplines and whether they are prepared to apply this knowledge in teaching;
- to evaluate the role of instructional factors in the persistence of pronunciation errors;
- to develop practical recommendations for improving the existing phonetic instructions.

The study assumes that stable pronunciation errors in Russian-speaking learners are influenced not only by the native language, but also by the way pronunciation is taught. If teachers do not actively apply contrastive linguistic knowledge and do not systematically address predictable difficulties, errors of this type are more likely to become fossilized.

During the investigation 4 main types of sources of learner-centred pronunciation errors were identified:

1. Articulatory apparatus and muscle memory – the muscles of the articulatory apparatus of the students are not used to the movements required to produce specific English sounds, such as nasal (e.g. /ŋ/ sound), aspirated consonants (e.g. /t^h/, /d^h/, and /p^h/ sounds) or interdental sounds (e.g. /ð/ and /θ/ sounds).
2. Orthographic (Visual) interference – a situation in which students struggle to pronounce words because they tend to misread them or lack knowledge of basic spelling-to-sound patterns (e.g. pronouncing island as /'i:slənd/ or /'aɪslænd/ instead of /'aɪlənd/).
3. Cognitive: paralogism (false analogy), morphological and syntactical unawareness. Paralogism occurs when the cognitive processes which are responsible for associations lead students to make seemingly logical, yet incorrect, assumptions (e.g. pronouncing said as /seɪd/ by analogy with paid, afraid and laid, instead of /sed/). Morphological unawareness refers to errors when students are unfamiliar with word-stress shifts and sound changes during word formation (e.g. pronouncing academic as /ə'kædemɪk/ – with the stress on the first syllable – by analogy with academy /ə'kædemɪ/ instead of /ækə'demɪk/). Syntactic unawareness results in errors caused by failing to identify the part of speech of a word, leading to incorrect phonetic realization (e.g. pronouncing the noun graduate as /'grædʒuət/ by analogy with the verb form, instead of /'grædʒuət/).
4. Auditory memory – occurs when students memorize an incorrect phonetic model of a word heard from an external source, such as a teacher or a non-native speaker (e.g. hearing someone, say a teacher, pronounce the word already as /'ɔ:lredi/, instead of /ɔ:l'redɪ/).

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